

Report Methodology

The Impact of Large Language Models in Finance: Towards Trustworthy Adoption

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We presented "The Impact of Large Language Models in Finance: Towards Trustworthy Adoption" report on March 27th at the Royal Institute. The report outlines a collective understanding of the impact, timeliness and significance of integrating LLMs into financial services among academia and industry. It is informed by a series of meetings and workshops with industry colleagues regarding the opportunities and risks associated with integrating LLMs into financial services.

This collective understanding is achieved following a rigorous methodology including three main stages. This technical paper describes the methodology of these studies.

As illustrated above, this report is a product of a three-stage process:

Stage 1 – Initial Report Preparation: In the final quarter of 2023, The Alan Turing Institute and HSBC produced a report on the impact of LLMs in banking as a result of an extensive literature survey. This research was part of the [FAIR Prosperity Partnership](#) to understand the challenges of using LLMs responsibly, through the lens of the five pillars of the FAIR programme (Robustness and Resilience; Privacy and Security; Fairness and Transparency; Verification and Accountability; and Integration Environment).

This report on LLMs in banking has become the basis for the current study by opening a broader discussion on LLMs in financial services. Then, the team from The Alan Turing Institute and HSBC conducted an extensive literature survey to identify the current applications and risks of LLMs in financial services.

Stage 2 – Workshop with Extended Focus: We invited attendees from major high-street banks, regulators, investment banks, insurers, payment services providers, as well as government and legal professionals working in financial services to hold a collective understanding workshop. Forty-three participants attended this workshop. Before the workshop, we shared our literature survey findings with the participants. During the workshop, we asked questions about the *likelihood*, *significance*, and *timing* of the impact of LLMs and related technologies on the financial services sector and beyond.

Our research team focused on understanding individual and sectoral perspectives on the use of LLMs in financial services, expanding the discourse to consider implications across the five pillars

of the FAIR program. We also asked questions related to individual and sectoral perceptions and collected answers using the Slido platform. Notetakers took notes during the open-ended questions and informal conversations.

Stage 3 – Overall analysis and reporting: We analysed the participants' responses and notetaker notes following a thematic analysis process and aligned the analysis findings with the previously identified opportunities and challenges. As a result, this report aligning with the pillars of the FAIR programme seeks to understand the scope, timing of adoption, barriers, benefits and potential impact of LLMs across the financial services sector.

Building upon the survey undertaken by the core team, the report follows a top-down approach starting with an overview and following in-depth discussions on thematic subjects. In the following sections, we present a brief history of the LLM applications, delve into opportunities and challenges of integrating LLMs in financial services, share the individual and sectoral perspectives from our expert group workshop, and discuss open-ended questions towards achieving safe utilisation of LLMs in financial services.

Stage 1: LLMs in Banking Report

Initial Conceptualisation

The initial research questions were aligned with the FAIR Prosperity Partnership's main objectives. The FAIR programme brings together academia and industry to advance research and develop practical and scalable solutions needed to fully realise the transformational benefits of responsible adoption of AI across the financial services industry. There are currently significant barriers to the adoption of these technologies which stem from a capability deficit in translating high-level principles concerning trustworthy design, development, and deployment of AI technologies including safety, fairness, privacy awareness, security, transparency, accountability, robustness, and resilience to concrete engineering, governance, and commercial practice. In developing an actionable framework for trustworthy AI, the major research challenge that needs to be overcome lies in resolving the tensions and trade-offs which inevitably arise between all these aspects when considering specific application settings. In this initial research objective conceptualisation, FAIR researchers sought to get insight into cross-disciplinary expertise from academia and industry.

Desk Research: Semi-structured Review

This report has been compiled by the core team comprising members from The Alan Turing Institute, as well as colleagues from HSBC, Accenture, and FCA. The initial focus of this report was to provide a historical overview of the subject, with particular attention to recent algorithmic and architectural advancements in the LLM domain and their application within the banking sector. The report, intended for internal distribution, followed a semi-structured review methodology. Leveraging impactful survey papers recently published, we identified pertinent literature in the field. The following papers served as the foundation for our review process:

- Zhao et al., "Revolutionizing Finance with LLMs: An Overview of Applications and Insights," arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.11641, 2024.
- Hadi et al., "A survey on large language models: Applications, challenges, limitations, and practical usage," TechRxiv, 2023.
- Bommasani et al., "On the opportunities and risks of foundation models," arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.07258, 2021.
- Maple et al., "The AI revolution: opportunities and challenges for the finance sector," arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.16538, 2023.

In addition to input from expert reviewers within the core team, we also examined recently published working papers and policy papers from both public sector and academic sources. Selected reports include:

- Bank of England, "Machine learning in UK financial services," London, 2022.
- Bank of England, Financial Conduct Authority, "The AI Public-Private Forum: Final report," 2022.

- International Monetary Fund, "ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: What AI means for economics," 2023.

Getting Feedback from Experts

We collected feedback from twelve colleagues from academia and industry. We asked for their feedback on the findings of the semi-structured review and their open questions. We included all these new inputs in this prior document.

This document has been disseminated to workshop participants to ensure a common understanding of the subject matter. Furthermore, it has presented several open questions to stimulate discussion before the workshop.

Stage 2: LLMs in Finance Collective Understanding Workshop

Objectives

We defined the key workshop objectives as follows:

- Presenting the summary of findings from the preliminary report on "LLMs in Finance," which is a joint product of researchers and practitioners from The Alan Turing Institute, HSBC, and FCA.
- Following the report findings, engaging in a comprehensive discussion on LLMs and their applications, delving into the insights derived from the preliminary report.
- Facilitating the collection of diverse perspectives within the group regarding the probability, significance, and timing of the technological impact stemming from LLMs.
- Leading a robust discussion to generate insights that can benefit not only industrial sectors but also regulatory and academic environments. The goal is to obtain a well-rounded understanding of the implications of LLMs.
- Harnessing the collective expertise of participants to generate valuable outputs that will serve as the foundational elements for an in-depth report. This report, launching at the Royal Institute in March, will encapsulate key findings and recommendations derived from the workshop discussions.

Questions

The questions are structured around three categories: (1) Personal perceptions to understand our participants' personal work-related experience, (2) Sectoral perceptions focusing on opportunities and challenges, likelihood and significance of the LLM integration-related issues, and (3) Thematic open-ended conversation. In the last set of questions, we determined five themes, aligned with FAIR's thematic areas: Robustness and resilience, privacy and security, fairness and transparency, verification and accountability, and integrity and environment.

The list of all questions asked in the workshop:

Personal Perception – Work related personal use
S1.1 - Are you personally utilising LLMs or any similar tools in your daily work? If so, select the tasks benefiting from the LLM integration.
S1.2 - Are you personally utilising LLMs or any similar tools in finance-related decision-making? How are you utilising LLMs in this decision-making process?
S1.3 - What risks do you identify when personally using LLMs in financial decision-making?
S1.4 - On a scale of 1 to 5, how robust are internal guidelines for utilising LLMs in your organisation?
S1.5 - What is missing in these "LLM internal use" guidelines?
Sectoral Perception – Likelihood, significance, timing

S2.1 - What are the most promising opportunities for integrating LLMs in financial decision-making processes?

S2.2.1 - When do you foresee the earliest integration of LLMs in public communication and engagement services (e.g. financial communication, customer interaction)?

S2.2.2 - When do you foresee the earliest integration of LLMs in financial insight generation services (e.g. market and trade surveillance, personal investment reports)?

S2.2.3 - When do you foresee the earliest integration of LLMs in the "money economics"-related services (e.g. treasury, venture capital, asset allocation)?

S2.2.4 - When do you foresee the earliest integration of LLMs in financial services safety (e.g. fraud detection, risk management)?

S2.4 - Integration of LLMs comes with a likelihood of adversarial impacts, in other words, risks. Rank these financial services categories based on their risk levels.

S2.5 - Which of the following would you consider as potential harms of integrating LLMs in public communication and engagement services (e.g. financial communication, customer interaction)?

S2.6 - Which of the following would you consider as potential harms of integrating LLMs in financial insight generation services (e.g. market and trade surveillance, personal investment reports)?

S2.7 - Which of the following would you consider as potential harms of integrating LLMs in the "money economics"-related services (e.g. treasury, venture capital, asset allocation)?

S2.8 - Which of the following would you consider as potential harms of integrating LLMs in financial services safety (e.g. fraud detection, risk management)?

S2.9 - What are the additional key challenges and risks associated with the implementation of LLMs in the finance sector?

Sectoral Perceptions – Thematic Open-Ended Conversation

S3.1 - Do we have clear definitions for the “robustness” of LLMs in order to understand/evaluate what “good” would look like in financial services?

S3.2 - Data asymmetry between large and small firms poses a significant challenge that can affect the development of robust LLM pipelines. What key technical and regulatory advancements do you believe could mitigate this data asymmetry issue?

S3.3 - Do we have clear definitions for the “security” of LLMs in order to understand/evaluate what “good” would look like in financial services?

S3.4 - Which potential privacy breaches can occur with the integration of LLMs into financial services?

S3.5 - Do we have clear definitions for the “fairness” of LLMs in order to understand/evaluate what “good” would look like in financial services?

S3.6 - What level of explainability and transparency do you believe is necessary to foster widespread adoption of LLMs within the financial services industry?

S3.7 - Do we have clear definitions for the “accountability” for LLMs in order to understand/evaluate what “good” would look like in financial services?

S3.9 - Do we have clear definitions for “integrity” in order to understand/evaluate what “good” would look like?

S3.10 - What skills do financial services professionals need to make sure they can effectively and successfully use LLM systems?

S3.11 - Developing and maintaining an LLM for a financial institution brings environmental and economic costs. Under what circumstances does investing in the development and maintenance of an LLM become beneficial for a financial institution?

Data Collection and Acknowledgement

- No digital recordings were made during the workshop. Instead, dedicated note-takers transcribed the conversation for documentation purposes.
- All data collected through online forms is treated with strict confidentiality and maintained in an anonymous format.
- Participants were granted the freedom to utilize information gathered during discussions for personal use. However, it was prohibited to disclose the identity or affiliation of speakers or any other participant without explicit consent.
- The following points are also explained to notetakers who attended this workshop:
 - o **Be Attentive to Nuances:** Pay close attention to subtle nuances, tone, and non-verbal cues during the discussion. These elements can provide valuable context and insights.
 - o **Clarify Ambiguities:** If there are any ambiguous or unclear points raised during the discussion, make a note to seek clarification from participants or facilitators for accurate documentation.
 - o **Maintain Neutrality:** Ensure that your tone in the conversation and your notes maintain a neutral tone, focusing on factual information and avoiding personal interpretations or biases.
 - o **Capture Action Items:** Identify any action items or tasks mentioned during the session. This information is crucial for follow-up and implementation after the workshop.
 - o **Respect Privacy:** Respect the privacy and confidentiality of participants. Avoid recording or noting any personal information that is not relevant to the discussion.

Flow

Part 1: Perceptions about integrating LLMs into their personal workplace. Views as an end-user. This part aims to understand participants’ perceptions about the utilisation of LLMs in their own workflow. Microsoft released a recent new future of work report, generalising many industries in one report. However, all sectors have unique challenges when it comes to internal use. This set of questions aims to understand participants’ perspectives on the utilisation of LLMs in a “financial service” workplace. It was a Slido survey (the answers were collected all at once with one submit button). In the end, we collected an overall understanding of the ‘personal utilisation’ of LLMs and participants’ perceptions about it.

Part 2: Participants’ expert views on LLMs in financial services. Answering from an organisational perspective. These questions focus on opportunities and challenges, likelihood and significance of the LLM integration-related issues. We collected the answers on Slido, revealed the answers after waiting around 2-3 minutes, and discussed the answers after each question.

Part 3: Open-ended thematic questions. We split the group into five to enable a discussion with active participation. The questions were displayed on the screen. The workshop leader explained the question. Following that, the participants within each group discussed this question in 8 minutes. The workshop leader prompted the groups on the timing. the notetaker recorded the key highlights of the discussion on Slido. This process took approximately 1-2 minutes. Once all groups compiled their highlights, the workshop leader presented the answers generated by each group. Subsequently, the workshop leader facilitated a broader discussion to build a collective understanding.

Figure 1. A total of five groups consisting of 7-8 participants discussed "what good would look like" separately.

Stage 3: Analysing and Aggregating Workshop Findings

Thematic Analysis

In this stage, we followed a rigorous thematic analysis strategy. Thematic analysis is a qualitative method used to identify, analyse, and interpret patterns or themes within data. It involves systematically organizing and categorizing data based on recurring ideas, concepts, or topics. Our thematic analysis is structured around a hierarchical taxonomy. The top level of this taxonomy includes the same five categories of the FAIR programme, which also shaped the open-ended conversation in the workshop. For each top-level category, we analysed the notetaker notes and Slido results based on:

- (1) **NIST's subcomponents for each category:** NIST's AI Risks Management Framework (2023) defines similar components for AI trustworthiness compared to our FAIR project principles. For example, robustness in this framework is linked with accuracy, reliability, validity, and generalizability, and types of failures are measured using specific metrics obtained from these other components. In our thematic categorisation, we consider these linked subcomponents to guide our analysis.
- (2) **Co-occurrences of concepts to define new subcomponents:** We utilised KeyBERT, an open-source Python library to conduct an NLP-based n-gram strategy. These co-occurrences helped researchers to support their categorisation to check the offered categorisation aligns with the statistical weight of the conversation topics.

A thematic analysis process traditionally begins with familiarization with the data, followed by generating initial codes to label relevant segments. These codes are then grouped into themes through a process of comparison and consolidation. Themes are refined and named, and the analysis is documented with supporting evidence from the data. In this structured analysis process, we used the subcomponents that occurred in the NIST's AI Risk Management Framework and extracted concepts from the n-gram analysis to create the labels.

Collating Workshop Findings and Prior Documents

During the report writing process, we systematically gathered information from various sources to ensure a comprehensive analysis. Firstly, we consolidated existing literature reviews, incorporating insights from prior research. Secondly, we integrated open-ended questions posed by participants and insights gleaned from workshops into our document, providing a multifaceted perspective. Additionally, we examined Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) and Bank of England staff working papers, along with joint reports about Machine Learning (ML) in the finance sector. By leveraging these resources, we aimed to capture relevant discussions and insights. This method allowed us to develop a thorough understanding and a nuanced view of Machine Learning Models (LLMs) within the finance domain.

Aggregating the Findings and Dissemination

Furthermore, to ensure the accuracy and relevance of our report, we solicited final feedback from workshop participants. We obtained input from ten participating organisations. Their valuable

insights and corrections were carefully incorporated into the final document. This iterative process helped to refine our analysis and enhance the overall quality of the report.

See the report at this link: https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2024-03/the_impact_of_large_language_models_in_finance_-_towards_trustworthy_adoption_1.pdf

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